

A NOTE ON AN ISOMER OF DIMETHYLETHYL PYRIDINE.

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The author was busy with a new synthesis of 2-methyl-4-ethylpyridine in order to identify some of the products of alkaline degradation of strychnine and brucine (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 396, 399) and in this connexion he prepared potassium salt of 2:6-dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine-3:5-dicarboxylic acid which gave normally 2:6-dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine but in one case the potassium salt was not decarboxylated for long and the product after mixing with soda lime was left in a beaker for four months (May to August during summer and rainy season). Afterwards, it was found that it had absorbed sufficient moisture and turned pasty. After drying at 100° in an air-oven it was distilled and it did not give even a trace of 2:6-dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine but a mixture of bases (a) b.p. $193-196^{\circ}$, (b) b.p. $217^{\circ}-220^{\circ}$. The latter was not sufficient for further characterisation but the former was converted into its picrate. The picrate was decomposed with aqueous sodium hydroxide and the base, extracted with petroleum ether, was washed with water and dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate. On removal of the solvent the base distilled completely at $195-96^{\circ}$ and was soluble in common organic solvents. It had strong smell of pyridine and like 2:6-dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine it did not fume in air. Owing to its volatility it could not be dried at 100° in *vacuo* and an undried sample of the material appeared to retain $1/4$ mol. of water. (Found in an undried sample: C, 76.83; H, 9.26; N, 9.88. $C_9H_{11}N$, $1\frac{1}{2} H_2O$ requires C, 76.75; H, 9.52; N, 9.76 per cent). The base gave crystalline salts with definite melting points.

The *hydrochloride* was prepared as a snow white crystalline mass from a solution of the base in ether by the addition of ethereal hydrogen chloride and recrystallised from alcohol in perfectly white thick prisms, m. p. 197° , and remained as such even after one year (2:6-dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine hydrochloride, prepared likewise, was hygroscopic, pinkish long needles, m. p. 97° , and on keeping turned liquid). It was soluble in alcohol, acetone, chloroform and water. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 62.95; H, 8.07; N, 8.72; Cl, 21.11. $C_9H_{11}N, HCl$ requires C, 62.97; H, 8.16; N, 8.16; Cl, 20.7 per cent). The *hydriodide* was prepared by mixing together alcoholic solutions of the hydrochloride and potassium iodide. The solution after addition of a little water was filtered and the residue on removal of the solvent was dissolved in ethyl acetate when the hydriodide separated in needles at room temperature. It is soluble in water, benzene, chloroform, and alcohol, m. p. 155° .

The *Ethiodide* in poor yield was obtained by mixing together chloroform solution of the base (1 mol.) and ethyl iodide (1.5 mol.) at room temperature as needles, m. p. 185°. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, benzene, chloroform and water.

The *Platinichloride* came down from dilute alcohol at 0° in golden yellow needles. It is soluble in chloroform, m.p. 222° (platinichloride of 2:6-dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine, m.p. 210°-211°; mixed m.p. 179°-181°). At 100° it lost 5.7% (H₂O requires 2.6 per cent). [Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 32.01; H, 4.22; N, 3.83; Pt, 28.58. (C₉H₁₃N, HCl)₂·PtCl₄ requires C, 31.77; H, 4.20; N, 4.12; Pt, 28.70 per cent].

The *Aurichloride* was prepared from dilute alcohol and was recrystallised from ethanol with a drop of gold chloride in yellow needles. It is soluble in alcohol, ethyl acetate, acetone, benzene and chloroform, m.p. 180°.

The *Picrate* was prepared by bringing together the solution of the base and picric acid and crystallised from hot methanol in lemon-yellow needles, m. p. 167° (2:6-dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine picrate, m. p. 120° and mixed m. p. 110°-135°). It lost at 100° in *vacuo* half a molecule of water of crystallisation (Found: H₂O, 2.3; ½ H₂O requires 2.4 per cent). [Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 49.64; H, 4.53; N, 15.59. C₉H₁₃N·C₆H₂(NO₂)₃(OH) requires C, 49.50; H, 4.40; N, 15.4 per cent].

From the analyses and other experimental observations it is quite evident that the base (a) b p. 195-96° agrees with formula C₉H₁₃N and is not identical with 2:6-dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine and other known bases of the series as the following comparison would show. The quantity was not sufficient for further work.

C ₉ H ₁₃ N	Hydrochloride.	Picrate	Platini chloride.	Aurichloride.
2:6-Dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine, b. p. 186° (<i>Annalen</i> , 231, 44; <i>J. Indian Chem. Soc.</i> , 1939, 16, 410, 415)	97°	120°	210°-211°	"
2-Ethyl-3:5-dimethylpyridine, b. p. 197°-199° (<i>Ber.</i> , 1890, 23, 685, 1110; <i>J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1923, 54, 428)	"	"	189°	81°-82° 86°-87°
2:5-Dimethyl-6-ethylpyridine, b. p. 181°-182° (<i>J. Indian Chem. Soc.</i> , 1935, 12, 665).	"	127°	"	"
2:6-Dimethyl-3-ethyl pyridine, b. p. 83-85°/23mm (<i>Ber.</i> , 1925, 58B, 194)	"	162°	178°	"
2:3:4:6-Tetramethyl pyridine, b. p. 180°-195° (<i>Ber.</i> , 1931, 54B, 569)	"	168°-70°	"	"
Base (a) b. p. 195°-196°	197°	167°	220°	180°

The micro-analyses were done by Dr. Ing. A. Schöller, Berlin.